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Plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition of Co_3O_4 thin films as a new approach for improving oxygen evolution activity

Dominik Knozowski^{a,b,*}, Aleksandra Kędzierska-Sar^{a,b}, Robert Ranecki^c, Piotr Kuświk^c, Maciej Fronczak^a, Stanisław Gierlotka^d, Sebastian Arabasz^e, Amil Aligayev^{f,g,h}, Ulkar Jabbarliⁱ, Francisco Javier Dominguez-Gutierrez^h, Marta Gmurek^{a,b}

^a Lodz University of Technology, Faculty of Process and Environmental Engineering, Wólczajska 213 St, Lodz 93-005, Poland

^b Lodz University of Technology, Faculty of Chemistry, Institute of General and Ecological Chemistry, Żeromskiego 116 St., Lodz 90-924, Poland

^c Institute of Molecular Physics, Polish Academy of Sciences, Mariana Smoluchowskiego 17 St., Poznań 60-179, Poland

^d Institute of High Pressure Physics (UNIPRESS), Polish Academy of Sciences, Laboratory of Nanostructures, Sokolowska 29/37 St., Warsaw 01-142, Poland

^e Łukasiewicz Research Network – PORT Polish Center for Technology Development, Stalowicka 147 St., Wrocław 54-066, Poland

^f CAS, Key Laboratory of High Magnetic Field and Iron Beam Physical Biology, Institute of Intelligent Machines, Hefei Institutes of Physical Science, Chinese Academy of Science, Hefei 230031, China

^g Science Island Branch of Graduate School, University of Science and Technology of China, Hefei 230026, China

^h NOMATEN Centre of Excellence, National Centre for Nuclear Research, A. Soltana 7 St., Otwock 05-400, Poland

ⁱ Institute of Theoretical Physics, Faculty of Physics, University of Warsaw, Pasteura 5 St, Warsaw 02-093, Poland

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ABSTRACT

The development of efficient and durable electrocatalysts for the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) remains a key challenge in advancing sustainable energy technologies. Among cobalt – based materials, spinel Co_3O_4 is a widely studied catalyst; however, its bulk form often suffers from poor electrical conductivity and limited accessibility of active sites. In this study, we demonstrate that plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition (PECVD), followed by thermal annealing in air, provides an effective route for vacancy engineering in Co_xO_y thin films inducing both oxygen and cobalt vacancies without relying on foreign dopants or ion-exchange processes. The Co_3O_4 films demonstrated exceptional OER performance, with the best sample achieving a low overpotential of 343 mV at 10 mA cm⁻², and a high capability for Co^{4+} formation, a key intermediate in the OER process. Additionally, the films exhibited catalytic activity not only at the surface, but also throughout their entire volume, highlighting the significance of deposition time and film thickness in optimizing OER performance. Ab-initio calculations, including Bader charge analysis and density of states evaluations, further elucidate the role of defect chemistry: oxygen vacancies enhance *OH adsorption and drive structural reconstruction, while cobalt vacancies reduce the energy barrier for deprotonation and facilitate the $\text{Co}^{3+} \rightarrow \text{Co}^{4+}$ oxidation process. Overall, this work establishes PECVD combined with thermal treatment as a powerful and scalable strategy for tailoring defect concentrations in cobalt oxide catalysts. The approach offers valuable insights into the rational design of high-performance OER catalysts, with broad implications for electrochemical energy conversion technologies.

1. Introduction

The Oxygen Evolution Reaction (OER) is an essential process for a

wide range of industrial applications, including water splitting, hydrogen generation, ammonia production, and carbon dioxide reutilization [1]. However, achieving efficient oxygen evolution remains

* Corresponding author at: Lodz University of Technology, Faculty of Chemistry, Institute of General and Ecological Chemistry, Żeromskiego 116 St., Lodz 90-924, Poland.

E-mail addresses: dominik.knozowski@p.lodz.pl (D. Knozowski), aleksandra.kedziarska-sar@p.lodz.pl (A. Kędzierska-Sar), robert.ranecki@ifmpan.poznan.pl (R. Ranecki), kuswik@ifmpan.poznan.pl (P. Kuświk), maciej.fronczak@p.lodz.pl (M. Fronczak), xray@unipress.waw.pl (S. Gierlotka), sebastian.arabasz@port.lukasiewicz.gov.pl (S. Arabasz), Amil.Aligayev@ncbj.gov.pl (A. Aligayev), u.jabbarli@student.uw.edu.pl (U. Jabbarli), Javier.Dominguez@ncbj.gov.pl (F.J. Dominguez-Gutierrez), marta.gmurek@p.lodz.pl (M. Gmurek).

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challenging, as it is a multistep, four-electron reaction that exhibits sluggish kinetics, irrespective of the pH of the environment [1–3]. High overpotentials – typically 300–400 mV above theoretical values – are often required for effective oxygen evolution, along with harsh, highly alkaline conditions [4]. While noble metals such as RuO₂ and IrO₂ are effective OER catalysts due to their excellent stability and low overpotentials, their high cost and limited availability hinder their widespread application [5,6]; thus much research has focused on developing cost-effective alternatives.

One of the most promising alternatives for RuO₂ and IrO₂ are transition metal oxides, in particular cobalt oxides (CoO_x). Cobalt's ability to exist in multiple oxidation states contributes to its catalytic versatility through redox flexibility and efficient interaction with reactants, intermediates, and products [7]. Moreover, cobalt oxides are cheap, abundant, and, what is most important, stable in alkaline environments. The family of cobalt oxides includes spinel Co₃O₄, rock-salt CoO, and hexagonal Co₂O₃ [6,8]. Among these, spinel Co₃O₄ has garnered the most attention because of its mixed valence states, particularly Co³⁺ and Co²⁺, which enable the formation of catalytically active Co⁴⁺ species [4, 9–14]. While the Co³⁺/Co⁴⁺ transition is believed to be key to enhanced OER activity, the structural and electronic conditions necessary to promote and stabilize Co⁴⁺ are still not fully understood. Studies suggest that cobalt vacancies and the reducibility of Co³⁺ sites may aid Co⁴⁺ formation during electrochemical process, while oxygen vacancies and tetrahedral Co²⁺ sites can facilitate OH⁻ adsorption [6,12,15–17]. However, the intrinsic limitations of bulk Co₃O₄ – such as low active site density, poor conductivity, and limited surface area – hinder the generation and stabilization of Co⁴⁺ [13,18]. The surface stability of Co⁴⁺ in Co₃O₄ is significantly enhanced when ion-exchange processes are applied, as these processes introduce structural modifications, such as lattice imperfections and oxygen vacancies, which stabilize higher oxidation states and improve catalytic performance for OER [2,5,16,17]. In contrast, stabilizing Co⁴⁺ in bulk Co₃O₄ is more challenging, as it lacks the structural and electronic alterations provided by ion-exchange, making the Co³⁺/Co⁴⁺ transition more difficult and less stable in the bulk material. These limitations can be addressed through strategies like cobalt and oxygen vacancy creation, surface defect engineering, nanostructuring and electrochemical activation, even without external doping, thereby enhancing Co⁴⁺ formation and stabilization [5,11,13,14,18–20]. Although significant progress has been made, stabilizing Co⁴⁺ in bulk Co₃O₄ remains a challenge, revealing an important gap in current knowledge and presenting a crucial direction for further research.

The introduction of such features can be achieved by either careful planning of the synthesis process, or by post-processing treatment, i.e. through plasma engraving [5,13,19,21] or thermal annealing [22]. Plasma engraving is in particular a very promising approach for Co₃O₄ modification, as it allows for expanding the surface area, improving the hydrophilicity, and introduction of structural defects [13,18]. Depending on the type of plasma (argon, oxygen, helium etc.) [23–25] various types of defects can be introduced. For example, argon plasma etching leads to cobalt reduction and oxygen/hydrogen removal thus leading to introduction of oxygen vacancies [13,19,21,25], while oxygen plasma causes oxidation of cobalt to Co³⁺ and introduction of surface peroxo (O₂⁻) species [24]. However, the main limitation of plasma engraving is that it only allows for surface treatment [26]. Extending the etching time to modify deeper parts of the material can damage the structure and lead to uncontrolled surface oxidation, ultimately deteriorating the catalyst's performance [27,28].

In this context, plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition (PECVD) is a material preparation technique that combines advantages of classical synthesis routes with plasma engraving. During the PECVD process, gaseous or vaporized molecular precursors are introduced into the plasma, then these precursors stepwise decompose into simpler species with simultaneous precipitation on substrate surface [29–31]. In this process, multiple concurrent phenomena take place, including

deposition, ablation (engraving), and surface modifications, resulting in layer-by-layer film growth. Because deposited material is constantly exposed to plasma, it can be expected that each of the several nanometers thick layers will be etched by plasma before the next layer is deposited. These interactions result in simultaneous material production and plasma treatment. The end result is a uniform layer of material similarly treated over the entire cross-section, with unique morphologies, and, potentially, highly defective structure, with cobalt and/or oxygen vacancies present in the bulk of thin film.

Inspired by these facts, in this study we aimed to address the challenges of stabilizing Co⁴⁺ species in Co₃O₄ for oxygen evolution reactions by introducing structural vacancies through utilizing PECVD technique. As a precursor, cobalt (I) cyclopentadienyldicarbonyl was selected due to its low boiling temperature, and absence of other elements than cobalt, oxygen, and carbon, according to the methodology described elsewhere [32]. The post-deposition thermal treatment transformed the material into spinel Co₃O₄ and promoted the creation of both cobalt and oxygen vacancies, critical for enhancing catalytic activity and stabilizing Co⁴⁺. This process significantly improved the oxygen evolution performance, achieving a potential of 343 mV at 10 mA cm⁻² for the most effective sample. Ab-initio calculations further support these findings, providing deeper insights into the vacancy mechanisms and catalytic behavior. This work not only fills a gap in understanding how to stabilize Co⁴⁺ in Co₃O₄ but also demonstrates how PECVD, along with thermal treatment, can offer an efficient route for enhancing OER performance and overcoming the intrinsic limitations of bulk Co₃O₄ catalysts.

2. Experimental and computational methods

2.1. Material preparation

PECVD has been applied to deposit the CoO_x-based thin films on glassy carbon in a parallel-plate radio-frequency (RF 13.56 MHz) reactor. Prior to deposition, glassy carbon bars (IKA Screening System, Germany) were cut into ~0.5 cm × 1 cm pieces and sonicated in isopropanol and n-hexane for 40 minutes to remove dust and greasy residues. Cobalt (I) cyclopentadienyldicarbonyl (CpCo(CO)₂, Sigma-Aldrich, USA) was used as cobalt precursor, while pure argon (99.999 %, Linde Gas, Poland) served as carrier gas. The precursor partial pressure was 0.2 Pa, while the partial pressure of argon was set on 5.8 Pa. The temperature of precursor was kept at 38 °C, while the temperature of upper electrode was ~80 °C, and the temperature of gas line was 50 °C. The glassy carbon substrates were one-sidedly coated with cobalt compounds using a glow discharge power of 60 W, and the deposition time ranged from 10 to 30 minutes. After the deposition, the samples were annealed at 400 °C in air atmosphere, with 15 °C/min temperature ramp, and 30 min dwell time, and finally cooled down naturally to room temperature. The thermal treatment in air led to Co₃O₄ formation [33]. The thermally treated samples are labeled as 10GC_Co₃O₄, 20GC_Co₃O₄, and 30GC_Co₃O₄, where the numbers 10, 20, and 30 denote the plasma exposure times in minutes. For the deeper insight, we also studied the 30GC_Co₃O₄ before thermal treatment. In the later sections of this work, this sample will be abbreviated as 30GC_CoO_x ASD. For better clarity, the labeling and description of the abbreviations used are presented in Table S1.

2.2. Structure characterization

The structure properties of as-deposited sample (i.e. without thermal treatment) as well as after annealing were characterized via different techniques including scanning electron microscopy (SEM), atomic force microscopy (AFM), X-ray diffraction (XRD) and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS).

SEM imaging of surfaces and cross-sections was performed using SEM Apreo 2S microscope (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) equipped

with an EDX Octan Elect Super spectrometer (EDAX, USA) and FIB/SEM Helios 450HP microscope (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA, formerly FEI Company). Samples prior to examination were attached to the specimen holder with carbon tape and were analyzed without coating at low accelerating voltage (<3.5 kV) under high vacuum mode ($p \sim 10^{-4}$ Pa). For high resolution imaging of the as deposited sample the beam deceleration was used. To determine the layer thickness, samples were fractured and mounted on the SEM stage with the fracture surface oriented upward for detailed examination, under previous conditions. Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) analysis was performed under 10 kV accelerating voltage, with the working distance of 10 mm from at least 3 measurements.

The surface topography of CoO_x on glassy carbon substrate was investigated using Atomic Force Microscopy under ambient conditions with an Agilent 5500 Scanning Probe Microscope (SPM) system. AFM images were acquired in contact mode using a Silicon Nitride (SiNi) Contact Mode AFM Probe (Budget Sensors, short probe with a nominal force constant of 0.27 N/m). The obtained surface topography images were processed using the open-source SPM analysis software Gwyddion [34]. Standard image processing steps included: shifting the minimal value to zero, leveling data by mean plane subtraction, correcting horizontal scars, aligning rows, and applying fast Fourier transform (FFT) filtering.

Diffraction measurements were performed using Panalytical X'Pert diffractometer with $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation in grazing-angle geometry. Parallel beam formed by a parabolic focusing mirror was incident onto the sample at an angle of 8° . The diffracted beam was recorded through the parallel-plate collimator with a resolution of 0.09° . Cobalt fluorescence was at the acceptable level due to the small thickness of the deposited layer. Its intensity was estimated by comparing the patterns to that of the bare glassy carbon substrate, and was subtracted from the data. Crystallite size was calculated from the width of the diffraction peaks using the Scherrer equation. Peak width used in the Scherrer formula was obtained after deconvoluting of the instrumental function from the data and extracting the single peak shape from the $\text{K}\alpha_1$ - $\text{K}\alpha_2$ doublet [35,36]. The instrumental resolution was determined by measuring the LaB_6 standard sample in the same grazing geometry and the $\text{K}\alpha$ doublet was decomposed by fitting with a pair of PearsonVI-shaped functions.

The analysis of the surface of the materials in order to describe the chemical composition and chemical states of the elements was performed by means of X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (AXIS Ultra spectrometer, Kratos Analytical Ltd., UK). The samples were attached to the bar with a small piece of carbon tape. The spectrometer was equipped with monochromatic $\text{Al K}\alpha$ X-rays (1486.6 eV). The spectra were gathered from 3 different areas (0.7×0.3 mm) of each sample under the pressure at the level of 10^{-9} Torr. The power of the anode was set at 180 W, and the hemispherical electron energy analyzer was operated at a pass energy of 20 eV for all the high-resolution measurements. All the measurements were carried out using a charge neutralizer (charge balance 3.6 V, filament current 1.6A, filament bias 1.6 V), and the main carbon peak (graphitic C 1 s at 284.6 eV) was taken for a final calibration of each spectrum. The fitting procedure involved subtracting the background using Shirley's method, followed by deconvolution of the spectra into individual components using Lorentz-Gaussian (30/70) peak shapes. The binding energy was referenced to the literature given in the detailed description of each spectrum in the regions Co 2p (785–775 eV), O 1 s (540–520 eV) and C 1 s (300–270 eV).

2.3. Electrochemical measurements

All of the electrochemical studies were conducted on potentiostat-galvanostat Autolab PGSTAT302N (Nova 2.1 software, Utrecht, The Netherlands). The measurements were conducted in three-electrode set-up, with platinum mesh as counter electrode, and saturated calomel electrode (SCE; EK-602, Eurosensor, Gliwice, Poland) as reference electrode. Measurements in acidic conditions (0.5 M H_2SO_4) were

performed without iR correction, while those carried on in alkaline conditions (1 M KOH) were conducted, if not otherwise stated, using 100 % iR correction, according to the suggestion of Zheng [37]. All potentials were calculated to the potential of reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE). Materials were characterized using cyclic voltammetry (CV), and linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) at the scan rate 20 mV s^{-1} . The electrochemical impedance spectroscopy was carried out with 10 mV amplitude, and with the frequency range of 100 kHz–10 Hz, at the potential of 0 V vs. reference electrode.

2.4. Computational modeling

Periodic ab-initio calculations are performed on the bulk of the Co_3O_4 spinel. The bulk is modelled using the 14-atom rhombohedral primitive unit cell with a lattice constant of 0.597 nm obtained by the XRD data shown in the experiments. Geometry optimization and electronic structure have then been performed using the Density Functional Theory (DFT) method implemented in the Vienna ab-initio Simulation Package (VASP) [38,39]. The ion-electron interactions employed the Projector Augmented Wave (PAW) pseudo-potential, and electron-electron interactions were described using a plane-wave basis set [40]. Atomic structural relaxation utilized the Generalized Gradient Approximation (GGA) method with the PBE0 model [40], which is a hybrid functional that incorporates a portion of exact Hartree-Fock exchange into the GGA framework of Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE). Bulks Co_3O_4 were simulated using a plane-wave expansion truncated at a cut-off energy of 550 eV. For the Brillouin-zone integration, a $(9 \times 9 \times 9)$ Monkhorst-Pack special k -points grid has been used. We carefully checked the convergence of the energy with respect to the k -points and plane-wave expansion. The plane-wave expansion was converged to $< 0.1 \text{ meV}/\text{\AA}^2$ [41,42] and a spin-unrestricted approach was employed [43,44]. The spin state has been optimized in the bulk Co_3O_4 by exploring multiple spin configurations. A full optimization of all atom positions was performed via the conjugate gradient optimization procedure and was concluded when the root-mean-square force on the atomic nuclei was $< 0.02 \text{ eV}/\text{\AA}$. Afterwards, samples with vacancies were separately obtained by removing one four-coordinated Co for Co^{2+} , three-coordinated Co for Co^{3+} , and an O atom for the anion O^{2-} , and the samples followed the same process of optimization than the one for the pristine case. The Density of States (DOS) of each sample were obtained by the tetrahedron method with Blöchl corrections [42].

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Structural characterization

SEM imaging was used to study morphology of obtained calcinated thin films. As shown in Fig. 1 a–c) all samples exhibit flat topography, however, multiple ripped ball-like defects are present on each film. As the deposition time was increased, fewer defects were observed. The presence of ripped ball-like defects can be explained by the properties of glassy carbon, which tends to crack upon heating in air atmosphere, creating defects with such shapes [45]. Longer deposition times led to better coverage of glassy carbon surface, thus in the case of 20GC- Co_3O_4 and 30GC- Co_3O_4 samples less cracks were observed. After contact with KOH solution, and subsequent electrochemical testing, the morphology of all samples was virtually unaffected (see Fig. S1 a–b) in Supporting info – SI). However, even after a short contact with H_2SO_4 , the cobalt oxide film disappeared almost completely, with small spots being the exception (Fig. S1 c–f) in SI). These results suggest that PECVD deposited Co_3O_4 thin films are vulnerable to highly acidic condition, similarly to CoO_x films obtained using other techniques [46].

To gain a deeper understanding of the structure, higher magnification surface images (Fig. 1 d–f) and cross-sectional views (Fig. 1 g–i) were obtained for each sample. These images show that the surface nanostructure exhibits a uniform thin-film morphology, treated

Fig. 1. SEM images of 10GC_Co₃O₄, 20GC_Co₃O₄, and 30GC_Co₃O₄ samples deposited with different deposition times. a)–f) surface view (d)–f) view on the surface at higher magnifications), g)–i) cross-sections.

consistently across the entire cross-section. The inner part of Co₃O₄ film is compact and without significant defects, with a hierarchically textured morphology. These observations suggest uniform, polycrystal growth of Co₃O₄ film on GC substrate during thermal treatment. The films deposited with durations of 10 min, 20 min and 30 min exhibit thickness of ~630 nm, ~1280 nm and ~1360 nm, respectively. These results indicate that the PECVD film growth rate is directly dependent on the deposition time.

To track the changes occurring during thermal treatment step, we compared the SEM images of the as-deposited and annealed samples. The results are given in Fig. 2 and Fig. S2 (SI). Under higher magnifications the difference between samples is visible. The as-deposited sample (Fig. 2 a) is compact and has a sub-micrometric structure resembling flat surface cauliflower. In contrast, the annealed sample reveals a homogeneous nanostructure composed of grains smaller than 50 nm, along with a highly porous architecture characterized by a

nanometric network of interconnected pores. The cross-sections of both materials (Fig. S2 in SI) confirm these initial observations. The thickness of as-deposited sample was much higher than annealed one (~2350 nm vs. ~1560 nm), which suggests shrinkage of the PECVD sample after thermal treatment, and, potentially, partial material loss.

Further superficial characterization was conducted using atomic force microscopy. Surface topography images taken for the sample before and after annealing reveal ball-like features, with structures locally protruding above the surface to a height of up to 400 nm, as shown in Fig. 3 a), c) and b), d), respectively. After annealing at 400 °C (Fig. 3 b), the surface transforms into a terrain resembling hilly landscapes (hills appearing light orange and valleys dark brown) accompanied by a reduced number of ball-like structures, which were also observed on SEM images (see i.e. Fig. S2 c) in SI). Despite these changes, distinct grains remain visible within the surface structure (Fig. 3 d) which are also detected by SEM (see Fig. 1 d, e, f).

Fig. 2. Detailed SEM images of as deposited 30GC_CoO_x ASD a) and thermal treated 30GC_Co₃O₄ b) samples.

Fig. 3. Surface topography images of the CoO_x -based on GC substrate: a) $20 \mu\text{m} \times 20 \mu\text{m}$ for 30GC_CoO_x ASD sample, b) $20 \mu\text{m} \times 20 \mu\text{m}$ for post annealed at 400°C sample ($30\text{GC_Co}_3\text{O}_4$), c) $5 \mu\text{m} \times 5 \mu\text{m}$ for 30GC_CoO_x ASD, d) $5 \mu\text{m} \times 5 \mu\text{m}$ for $30\text{GC_Co}_3\text{O}_4$.

The grain size distribution analysis was conducted using the “watershed” algorithm implemented in Gwyddion [34]. For each identified grain, the equivalent disk radius was calculated. This method projects the grain area onto a horizontal plane, and assumes a circular shape for the area. A comparison of the grain size distribution between the two samples is presented in Fig. S3. The grain size distributions for both samples are quite similar. However, the annealed sample shows an increase in larger grains, and a decrease in smaller grains compared to the as-deposited sample, as indicated by the blue arrow in Fig. S3. This observation suggests that the grain growth is a result of the annealing process.

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of all the synthesized cobalt oxide films on glassy carbon are shown in Fig. 4. All samples exhibit several broad maxima typical for amorphous structure with diffraction peaks at about 25° and 43° , corresponding to the graphitic crystallite planes (0 0 2) and (1 0 0), respectively [47,48]. These peaks originate from glassy carbon substrate as evidenced by comparison with the diffraction pattern of pure GC shown by the curve at the very bottom of the diagram. Apart from the amorphous maxima the patterns of the heat treated films $10\text{GC_Co}_3\text{O}_4$, $20\text{GC_Co}_3\text{O}_4$, $30\text{GC_Co}_3\text{O}_4$ show presence of sharp diffraction peaks indicating a polycrystalline structure in those films. The peaks at 18.9 , 31.3 , 36.9 , 59.4 and 65.3 can be unequivocally identified as (111), (220), (311), (511) and (440) reflections of Co_3O_4 spinel structure respectively. The standard pattern of cobalt spinel listed in JCPDS record 42–1647 is shown in Fig. 4 for reference. The intensity of the peaks increase with longer deposition times, indicating a stronger crystallographic alignment with a prominent (311) peak observed at 36.9° . The average crystallite size of the particles calculated from the broadening of the diffraction peaks is approximately 30 nm, similar for all cases. In the pattern of the as-deposited film 30GC_CoO_x no spinel peaks are present meaning that such film is amorphous [32].

In order to study the structure of obtained films, we gathered the XPS spectra. First, we investigated the elemental composition of each film. The results are collected in Table S2, while the full spectra are given in

Fig. 4. XRD pattern of $10\text{GC_Co}_3\text{O}_4$, $20\text{GC_Co}_3\text{O}_4$, $30\text{GC_Co}_3\text{O}_4$, 30GC_CoO_x ASD and pure GC with comparison of the standard patterns of Co_3O_4 (JCPDS card no. 42–1467).

Fig. S4 in SI. In all investigated samples (both as-deposited and thermally treated) cobalt, carbon as well as oxygen were detected which is consistent with literature reports where $\text{CpCo}(\text{CO})_2$ was used as a precursor in PECVD [49,50]. Moreover, EDS spectrum confirms the presence of only Co, C, O elements in the whole volume of the sample (Fig. S5 in SI).

Next, we studied the chemical changes occurring during the pyrolysis process. In the as-deposited 30GC_CoO_x ASD sample the major component was carbon (over 60 %), which originated from unburnt carbonyl- and cyclopentadienyl-derived compounds [51]. This carbon potentially exists in the form of sp^2 (284.6 eV) and sp^3 (285.5 eV) carbon structures, as indicated by the peaks at 286.6, 288.1, and 289 eV in C 1 s XPS (Fig. S6 a) in SI) and, as further supported by the O 1 s XPS peak at 532 eV, in the form of carbonyl or organic $\text{C}=\text{O}$ (Fig. S7 a) in SI) [52,53]. In contrast, the $30\text{GC_Co}_3\text{O}_4$ layers revealed 4 times lower carbon share (~60 % vs. ~15 %). After calcination in air atmosphere, the majority of organic carbon is burnt off, which was already discussed in previous works [32]. It is important to note that no cobalt-carbon bonding is observed, either in the as-deposited state or after thermal treatment, as indicated by the absence of a ~283 eV peak in the C 1 s bands (Fig. S6 a) and b) in SI), which is in agreement with [50].

Fig. 5 a) shows the high-resolution XPS spectrum of the cobalt oxide thin films. The $30\text{GC_Co}_3\text{O}_4$ sample exhibits a Co 2p core-level spectrum with a spin-orbit energy separation of 15 eV: a Co $2\text{p}_{3/2}$ peak at 779.6 eV with a satellite peak at 789 eV, and a Co $2\text{p}_{1/2}$ peak at 794.7 eV with a satellite at 804 eV – features characteristic of Co_3O_4 [54]. The spectral profile and binding energy position of the Co $2\text{p}_{3/2}$ peak and cobalt Auger parameter (1552.6 eV – see Fig. S4 in SI) confirm the formation of Co_3O_4 and exclude the presence of CoO [30,31]. This identification is further supported by XRD analysis, which confirms the exclusive presence of the Co_3O_4 spinel phase. Similar Co 2p spectral features were observed for the other two thin films (Fig. 5 b). In contrast, the 30GC_CoO_x ASD sample exhibits a Co $2\text{p}_{3/2}$ main peak at 781 eV with a satellite at 787 eV, and a Co $2\text{p}_{1/2}$ peak at 796 eV with a satellite at 803 eV, consistent with the CoO phase [54]. The $\text{GC_Co}_3\text{O}_4$ samples also exhibit two peaks in the O 1 s region (Fig. S7 b in SI). The first peak, at a binding energy of 529.8 eV, corresponds to lattice oxygen [55]. The second peak, at 531.1 eV, is typically associated with oxide defect states, surface hydroxylation, or differential charging effects in thin films [56, 57]. In contrast, the 30GC_CoO_x ASD sample exhibits a dominant O 1 s feature at 531.5 eV, which corresponds to oxygen in CoO or $\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2$ [57–59] (Fig. S7 a) in SI).

Fig. 6 a) presents the Co $2\text{p}_{3/2}$ XPS spectra for $\text{GC_Co}_3\text{O}_4$ samples with different deposition times after calcination. The Co $2\text{p}_{3/2}$ XPS spectra of all samples reveal one broad signal between 778–782.5 eV. The intensity Co $2\text{p}_{3/2}$ bands increases with the deposition time, and it is

the highest for $30\text{GC_Co}_3\text{O}_4$ sample. After deconvolution, two new peaks appeared, one centered at 779.7 eV, corresponding to Co^{3+} , and second at 781.2 eV, assigned as Co^{2+} . These results suggest the existence of spinel cobalt oxide (Co_3O_4), based on the co-existence of Co^{2+} and Co^{3+} [49,50]. The relative ratio between Co^{3+} and Co^{2+} is given in Table 1. The $\text{Co}^{3+}/\text{Co}^{2+}$ ratio oscillates around 1.23–1.43, which indicates slight deficiency of Co^{3+} form in comparison to ideal Co_3O_4 spinel (2.0). This deficiency may originate from the following phenomena: (i) presence of Co^{3+} vacancies, (ii) presence of oxygen vacancies [60].

In contrast to annealed materials (Fig. 6 b), as-deposited samples revealed an additional band at 778.4 eV, corresponding to metallic Co^0 . Moreover, in as-deposited samples Co^{2+} dominates, and Co^{3+} is hardly present. These results are in agreement with [61], where amorphous CoO_x was composed with cobalt in the oxidation states of Co^0 , Co^{2+} , and Co^{3+} . These records indicate that during the annealing step part of Co^{2+} is oxidized to Co^{3+} , which is consistent with previous reports. In addition, preferential Co^{2+} formation with oxygen vacancies is typical for Ar plasma treatment [13]. Moreover, it is well known that amorphous metal oxides often exhibit a higher concentration of oxygen vacancies compared to their crystalline counterparts, which can significantly influence their catalytic activity and other properties [62].

The influence of electrochemical tests on $\text{GC_Co}_3\text{O}_4$ materials was assessed by comparing the Co $2\text{p}_{3/2}$ spectra between the pristine sample and the one after cyclic voltammetry test. The results are presented in Table S3 and in Fig. S8 (in SI). After electrochemical testing, a steady increase of $\text{Co}^{3+}/\text{Co}^{2+}$ from 1.23 to 1.73 was recorded. This observation suggests that applying high positive potential leads to partial oxidation of spinel $30\text{GC_Co}_3\text{O}_4$, whose $\text{Co}^{3+}/\text{Co}^{2+}$ ratio approached the ratio of ideal spinel structure (2.0), but both oxidation states remained even after prolonged cycling, which is consistent with previous reports [63].

Due to the carbon burden, the chemical composition of the annealed thin films was affected by deposition time, showing an increase in oxygen content and a decrease in carbon content. A similar trend was reported by [49] during the fabrication of Co_3O_4 via PECVD followed by annealing, using a $\text{CpCo}(\text{CO})_2$ precursor and argon carrier gas. As can be seen in Table S2 (in SI), although the carbon content decreased after thermal treatment, it still remained high. However, based on the XPS O 1 s results (Fig. S7 in SI), only a small amount of carbon was bonded to oxygen, while the majority of oxygen was bonded to cobalt, as indicated by the peaks at 529.8 eV (Co–O) and 531.1 eV (Co–OH) [60]. Based on the data, the atomic percentage of oxygen bonded to cobalt slightly increased with deposition time, 92.2 %, 92.7 %, and 93.8 % for $10\text{GC_Co}_3\text{O}_4$, $20\text{GC_Co}_3\text{O}_4$, $30\text{GC_Co}_3\text{O}_4$ samples, respectively. Meanwhile, the cobalt content varied with deposition time, reaching 31 % after 10 minutes, increasing to 33 % after 20 minutes, and decreasing to 30 % after 30 minutes. After reconsidering the cobalt-oxygen bonding

Fig. 5. XPS spectra of Co 2p region for: a) selected sample after ($30\text{GC_Co}_3\text{O}_4$) and before calcination (30GC_CoO_x ASD), b) $\text{GC_Co}_3\text{O}_4$ thin films deposited with various deposition times.

Fig. 6. a) Co $2p_{3/2}$ XPS fitting spectra of GC- Co_3O_4 samples deposited with various deposition times, b) comparison between Co $2p_{3/2}$ XPS spectra of selected sample after (30GC- Co_3O_4) and before calcination (30GC- CoO_x ASD).

Table 1

Core level binding energy intensity data of plasma – deposited cobalt oxide layers with various deposition times.

Sample	Co ³⁺ (at% share)	Co ²⁺ (at% share)	Co ⁰ (at% share)	Ratio Co ³⁺ /Co ²⁺
10GC- Co_3O_4	57.09	42.91	0	1.33
20GC- Co_3O_4	58.76	41.24	0	1.42
30GC- Co_3O_4	55.10	44.90	0	1.23
30GC- CoO_x ASD	6.32	90.93	2.75	0.07

in obtained Co_3O_4 , the Co/O ratio is found to be 0.58, 0.70 and 0.71 for 10GC- Co_3O_4 , 20GC- Co_3O_4 , 30GC- Co_3O_4 samples, respectively, suggesting the potential presence of cobalt vacancies. This is in agreement with data indicating that annealing at temperatures above 200 °C leads to the formation of cobalt vacancies [33,64–66].

Considering that plasma treatment in Ar as well as the oxygen vacancy formation during PECVD [67,68] it can be suspected that oxygen vacancies are created in 30GC- CoO_x ASD, which are reduced during annealing. Therefore, we concluded that after PECVD and thermal treatment the coexistence of oxygen vacancies and cobalt vacancies is highly possible.

3.2. Electrochemical measurements

To investigate the OER electrocatalytic activity of plasma deposited Co_3O_4 films, linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) in 1 M KOH was conducted. The results are depicted on Fig. 7. The recorded onset potential in the case of all PECVD produced material was below 0 V vs. SCE. This result further suggests the deficiency of Co^{3+} ions in the cobalt structure [64]. The OER overpotentials measured at 10 mA cm^{-2} (η_{10}) equal 355 mV, 357 mV, 343 mV for 10GC- Co_3O_4 , 20GC- Co_3O_4 , and 30GC- Co_3O_4 samples, respectively. The electrochemical activity is comparable in the case of each sample, however longer deposition times leads to slight decrease of OER overpotential, which is favorable for oxygen evolution processes. This is in contrast to previous works concerning plasma post-processing, where extending the plasma exposure caused deterioration of electrochemical performance [13]. Comparing the obtained η_{10} (~350 mA cm^{-2}) with literature reports, PECVD produced films exhibited decent performance in comparison to other Co_3O_4 spinel materials (310–420 mV at η_{10}) [69–71]. High electrochemical performance is usually explained as the effect of presence of oxygen and cobalt vacancies, which should be created during our materials' fabrication process.

The electrochemical activity in plasma deposited CoO_x thin films was

Fig. 7. Linear sweep voltammetry for GC- Co_3O_4 layers deposited on glassy carbon. Scan rate: 20 mV s^{-1} , electrolyte: 1 M KOH.

further analyzed by cyclic voltammetry (CV) Fig. 8 a) and b) depicts CV curves obtained in KOH and H_2SO_4 . As shown on Fig. 8 a), in 1 M KOH, two characteristic redox transition appeared: a weak wave at ~1.35 V, and the peak at ~1.48 V. Besides, a steep current increase was recorded, attributed to the oxygen evolution reaction. The anodic peaks correspond to transition from Co^{2+} to Co^{3+} , and from Co^{3+} to Co^{4+} , respectively, according to reactions 1) and 2) [14]:

The reverse sweep revealed the broad feature in the potential range of 1–1.5 V, which corresponds to the reduction counterpart of reaction 1) and 2). According to previous reports [8,72] the 2) redox process occurs predominantly at spinel form of CoO_x , and can only take place on Co^{2+} tetrahedral sites of the spinel. This further confirms the presence of Co_3O_4 cobalt oxide form in PECVD obtained samples. The current response changes with sample deposition time, and it is the highest for 30GC- Co_3O_4 . This observation suggests that electrochemical activity was proportional to layer thickness. Fig. S9 a) (SI) demonstrates the comparison between CV curves for annealed, as-deposited and pure glassy carbon samples. In contrast to annealed samples, no other peaks were observed for as-deposited and pure glassy carbon samples, besides

Fig. 8. Electrochemical studies for PECVD deposited Co_3O_4 layers on glassy carbon substrate. a, b) Cyclic voltammograms, scan rate: 20 mV s^{-1} , 2nd scan c, d) Electrochemical impedance spectra.

the response coming from oxygen evolution. The oxygen evolution potential is $\sim 130 \text{ mV}$ and 950 mV higher in the case of as-deposited and pure glassy carbon, respectively, in comparison to annealed samples, which underlines the importance of calcination and $\text{CoO}_x \rightarrow \text{Co}_3\text{O}_4$ transformation for oxygen evolution reaction.

In contrast to KOH solution, in H_2SO_4 electrolyte (Fig. 8 b) all materials show only the electrochemical response related to oxygen evolution. The shape of the curves was common for all studied thin films, and it is no different for as-deposited and pure glassy carbon samples (see the comparison on Fig. S9 b) in SI). The potential OER depends however on the material, and it equals 2.53 V , 2.08 V , $1.86\text{--}1.9 \text{ V}$ at η_{10} for glassy carbon, as-deposited, and annealed samples, respectively. Such variations can be explained by differences in catalytic activity between each set of samples. One may notice that the OER potential of annealed samples stays the same independently of deposition time. The results, along with SEM imaging indicate, that although in H_2SO_4 the CoO_x layer was removed, there were still residuals of cobalt species preserved mainly in the pores of glassy carbon (see Fig. S1 c)–f) in SI), which catalyzed the evolution of oxygen, and thus lowers the OER potential. The explanation of this phenomenon was given by Zhou et al. [73], who suggested, that in acidic conditions Co^{2+} easily dissolves, while providing little-to-no contribution to catalytic activity, while the remaining Co^{3+} may still catalyze the oxygen evolution reaction.

The materials were further tested by means of electrochemical impedance spectroscopy. Nyquist plots for freshly prepared layers are presented in Fig. 8 c) and d). In alkaline environment, pure glassy carbon exhibits only straight vertical line, which indicates the formation of electrical double layer on the surface. In contrast, the annealed samples

revealed a distinct semicircle followed by a 45° line. The semicircle in the high frequency region represents charge transfer resistance, while the straight line at low frequencies corresponds to Warburg impedance of ion diffusion process. Interestingly, with the extension of the deposition time the charge transfer resistance steadily decrease, which indicates facile surface reaction between catalyst and water. These results further prove longer deposition time has beneficial effect on the OER performance of the annealed samples. In comparison to alkaline environment, in the acidic conditions all samples exhibit only the vertical line, similar to glassy carbon substrate. These spectra further confirm that the CoO_x layer was removed, and thus we observe only the typical glassy carbon response. The slight differences between PECVD deposited Co_3O_4 layers and pure GC arose from the residual Co^{3+} species, which were also observed on Fig. S1 (in SI).

The electrochemical stability was examined on best performing 30GC_ Co_3O_4 by recording 100 consecutive cyclic voltammograms (CV) (Fig. 9). The electrochemical response and shape of the CV curve, including $\text{Co}^{3+} \rightarrow \text{Co}^{4+}$ transition peak, were stable over the entire testing period. However, a steady decrease in $\text{Co}^{3+} \rightarrow \text{Co}^{4+}$ transition current was observed, roughly by 23 % after 100 cycles. Yet, further washing and reusing the electrode, the current density of $\text{Co}^{3+}/\text{Co}^{4+}$ transition returned to the initial level. Therefore, we attribute this current density loss to oxygen bubbles formation and partial blockage of the access to the electrode, leading to lower exposure of active surface to electrolyte, which occurred despite using 6 mA cm^{-2} current density limit. Alternatively, the material deterioration could be caused by diffusion of ionic species into material, partial dissolution of active species, or oxidation of Co^{2+} to Co^{3+} [74,75]. The latter is most likely as

Fig. 9. Stability test for 30GC_Co₃O₄ sample by cyclic voltammetry. Scan rate: 50 mV s⁻¹, electrolyte: 1 M KOH. The electrode was not rotated, nor oxygen bubbles were removed during the measurement. Results without iR correction.

material oxidation was also indicated by XPS spectra (see Table S3 and Fig. S8 in SI). Nevertheless, more stability testing has to be performed to properly evaluate electrochemical durability.

One thing worth noting, is that the electrochemical response of Co³⁺ → Co⁴⁺ transition of 30GC_Co₃O₄ thin film is exceptionally high in comparison to other un-doped spinel materials reported in the literature. The comparison of Co³⁺ → Co⁴⁺ transition current between our sample with selected literature reports, along with typical electrochemical parameters, is given in Table 2. It has been stated that the presence of Co⁴⁺ intermediate has a significant impact on many electrochemical reactions, including oxygen evolution [76]. Interestingly, according to previous studies [6,77], higher OER activity and higher Co³⁺ → Co⁴⁺ transition current is related mostly to the presence of Co³⁺ in the octahedral sites. However, in our case, both XPS spectra and onset potential show deficiency of Co³⁺ at the surface region. Besides, the XRD

spectra also did not reveal any preferential plane exposure, which could explain the unusual activity of our materials. Therefore, the unusual electrochemical response is believed to be linked to structural defects, not only on the surface of the material but also in the deeper layers of the film, which might support our hypothesis regarding the presence of these defects. As for the other parameters, like Tafel slope, OER overpotential and onset potential, our material performs above average in comparison to literature reports.

3.3. Computational methods

According to previous reports and experimental data in this work, surface plasma treatment leads to enlargement of surface area and introduction of mainly oxygen vacancies in external layers of spinel Co₃O₄ [24]. However, to the best of our knowledge, there are no studies concerning vacancies' formation in bulk material during plasma treatment followed by thermal annealing and its characterization for catalytic applications. Therefore, we conducted computational modelling to predict the type and concentration of vacancies and their potential impact on electrochemical performance. In the first step, we estimated the stability of various defected spinels by calculating density of states. Vacancies in a material significantly impact the DOS by disrupting the periodicity of the crystal lattice and altering the local electronic environment. One prominent effect is the introduction of localized midgap states, caused by dangling bonds or altered coordination of neighboring atoms, leading to extra peaks in the DOS with respect to the pristine case, as shown in Fig. 10. Vacancies can also narrow the band gap by introducing defect states near the valence band maximum (VBM, analogous to the HOMO) or conduction band minimum (CBM, analogous to the LUMO), effectively smearing the gap edges; this effect is mainly observed for the anion O²⁻ vacancies (see Fig. 10 c) [43,81]. Additionally, vacancies influence carrier concentrations; cation vacancies, such as Co²⁺, act as acceptors as shown in Fig. 10 b), enhancing p-type conductivity, while anion vacancies, such as O²⁻, act as donors as depicted in Fig. 10 c), increasing n-type conductivity, often shifting the Fermi level accordingly.

Magnetic effects may also arise, as vacancies create unpaired electrons, inducing localized magnetic moments, which are illustrated in Fig. 10 for the spin-resolved DOS as asymmetry between spin-up and

Table 2
Comparison of OER activity parameters for Co₃O₄ obtained by various methods.

Material	Preparation method of Co ₃ O ₄	Structure	Current response of Co ³⁺ → Co ⁴⁺ transition	Tafel slope (mV dec ⁻¹)	OER over-potential (mV)	Onset potential (V)*	Ref.
Thin-layer Co ₃ O ₄ on GC	PECVD	Ball-like	3.7 mA cm ⁻² (20 mV s ⁻¹ , 1 M KOH) ~6 mA cm ⁻² (50 mV s ⁻¹ , 1 M KOH)	58.7	343	1.51	Our work
Co ₃ O ₄ on GC	Direct phase transformation of hexagonal CoO on GC	–	~ 2 mA cm ⁻² (20 mV s ⁻¹ , 0.1 M KOH)	58.7	317	1.48	[63]
Binder-assisted Co ₃ O ₄ , Nafion binder	Commercial	–	~ 1.5 mA cm ⁻² (20 mV s ⁻¹ , 0.1 M KOH)	61.3	–	1.52	[63]
Co ₃ O ₄ on Pt	Sol-gel	Porous, with indistinctly formed grains and uneven surface	~0.45 mA cm ⁻² (10 mV s ⁻¹ , 1 M KOH)	55–60	441	1.59	[64]
Co ₃ O ₄ powder deposited on GC	hydrothermal	Regular cubes	~ 1.6 mA cm ⁻² (50 mV s ⁻¹ , 0.1 M KOH)	59	590	1.61	[6]
Co ₃ O ₄ powder deposited on GC	hydrothermal	Regular octahedra	~0.1 mA cm ⁻² (50 mV s ⁻¹ , 0.1 M KOH)	67	550	1.61	[6]
Co ₃ O ₄ nanowires	Template	Nanowires	~2.5 mA cm ⁻² (50 mV s ⁻¹ , 1 M KOH)	52	392	1.53	[78]
Co ₃ O ₄ powder	hydrothermal	Crushed nuts	~2 mA cm ⁻² (1 mV s ⁻¹ , 1 M KOH)	65.2	433	1.62	[79]
Co ₃ O ₄	Sol-gel	Featureless	~0.5 mA cm ⁻² (5 mV s ⁻¹ , 1 M NaOH + peroxymonosulfate)	–	370	1.45	[80]
Co ₃ O ₄ with cobalt vacancies	Ammonia route	Amorphous	~ 3 mA cm ⁻² 50 mV s ⁻¹ , 1 M KOH	38.2	268	1.42	[12]

* information extracted from charts included in cited works

Fig. 10. Density of states (DOS) of spinel Co_3O_4 : a) Pristine case, shown alongside the optimized unit cell. b) DOS illustrating the effects of cation vacancies (Co^{2+} and Co^{3+}), presented with the corresponding unit cell used for simulations. c) DOS highlighting the impact of an anion (O^{2-}) vacancy, shown next to the associated unit cell.

spin-down states. As shown in Fig. 10 b), removing O^{2-} reduces the contribution of oxygen 2p orbitals to the valence band, leading to a shift in the DOS and a reduction in the bandwidth of the valence states. Furthermore, the presence of Co^{2+} or Co^{3+} vacancies can lead to broadening of DOS peaks due to the disruption of symmetry and periodicity, localizing electronic states and smearing energy distributions as observed in Fig. 10 b). The removal of Co ions reduces the contributions of Co-3d orbitals to the DOS, particularly near the Fermi level, leading to changes in the material's conductivity. As noted, Co^{2+} ions form stronger interactions with adjacent oxygen 2p orbitals compared to Co^{3+} . The removal of Co^{2+} ions disrupts these interactions, resulting in changes in hybridization and shifting the DOS near the Fermi level. These changes influence a material's optical and electrical properties, potentially introducing sub-bandgap absorption.

The formation of Co^{2+} , Co^{3+} , and oxygen vacancies in the spinel Co_3O_4 structure is then analyzed by computing the vacancy formation energy $E_{VF} = E_{N-1} - (N-1/N)E_N$ [82,83] where E_N and E_{N-1} are the total energies of the pristine and defective structures, respectively. The results show that the oxygen vacancy formation energy is -3.19 eV, indicating moderate stability for oxygen vacancies in the spinel lattice. The calculated E_{VF} values reveal significant differences in vacancy stability depending on the type of defect: oxygen vacancies exhibit the lowest energy, indicating their higher thermodynamic favorability. In contrast, Co^{2+} and Co^{3+} vacancies show formation energies of -5.52 eV, and -5.95 eV, respectively, suggesting less favorable formation under comparable conditions, in good agreement with reported data for the perfect case [84]. These results highlight the tendency of Co_3O_4 to accommodate oxygen vacancies more readily, which may play a crucial role in its catalytic and electronic behavior, particularly in redox reactions [5]. The distinct vacancy formation energies further highlight the impact of defect types on the stability and reactivity of the spinel structure.

To characterize the spinel Co_3O_4 with cobalt (Co) and oxygen (O) vacancies, which influence the material's catalytic properties, we calculate several key thermodynamic and electronic parameters. We first calculate the energy values for the ϵ_{VBM} and the ϵ_{CBM} of all the systems which allow us to compute the gap $E_g = \epsilon_{CBM} - \epsilon_{VBM}$, chemical potential $\mu = (\epsilon_{CBM} + \epsilon_{VBM})/2$ which represents the change in the Gibbs free energy of a system as the number of particles varies, providing information of the stability and reactivity of the system. The chemical hardness $\eta = (\epsilon_{CBM} - \epsilon_{VBM})/2$ quantifies the material's resistance to changes in its electron distribution, serving as a measure of its electronic stability. Electronegativity $\chi = -\mu$ is a measure of an atom's ability to attract and hold electrons when forming a chemical bond, influencing the bond strength and reactivity. Atomic electronegativity, though inherently an atomic-scale property, significantly influences the structural and electronic characteristics of extended solids. Differences in electronegativity can lead to charge transfer, shift orbital energies, and alter band alignment and band gap width. Thus, it plays a key role in tuning the electronic properties of multicomponent materials. Finally, electrophilicity $\omega = \mu^2/2\eta$ reflects the ability of an atom or molecule to accept electrons, with higher values indicating stronger electron-accepting tendencies, which is crucial in catalysis [44]. In Table 3, we present DFT calculations of these parameters in eV, which provide

Table 3

VBM, CBM, CBM-VBM gap (E_g), chemical potential (μ), chemical hardness (η), electronegativity (χ), and electrophilicity (ω) in eV.

Parameter	Pristine	Co^{2+}	Co^{3+}	O^{2-}
CBM	-5.54	-3.40	-4.34	-5.86
VBM	-8.08	-3.54	-4.48	-7.51
E_g	2.54	0.14	0.14	1.65
μ	-6.81	-3.46	-4.41	-6.68
η	1.27	0.07	0.07	0.83
χ	6.81	3.46	4.41	6.68
ω	18.2	83.6	137	27.0

information into the electronic properties that govern the catalytic behavior of Co_3O_4 with vacancies [5]. It is worth noting that the functional used in the DFT calculations provides results that are in good agreement with experimental data, with the bandgap (E_g) for the pristine case being 2.54 eV. In contrast, using the standard PBE functional would yield an underestimated value of 0.19 eV, especially in the case of an oxygen vacancy. For the oxygen vacancy, our calculation gives a bandgap of 1.65 eV, while PBE would predict 0.11 eV, not accounting for the charge redistribution among atoms due to the absence of an oxygen atom [85,86]. Additionally, DFT-derived global reactivity descriptors—chemical potential (μ), chemical hardness (η), electronegativity (χ), and electrophilicity index (ω)—showed that structures containing cobalt vacancies possessed the lowest values of all four parameters. This implies greater electronic softness and a higher tendency to accept electrons, which mechanistically supports the experimentally observed increase in OER activity via facilitated charge transfer and lower energy barriers for intermediate formation. These electronic changes directly correlate with the enhanced OER performance observed in our PECVD-grown thin films. The oxygen vacancies introduced during deposition are known to create mid-gap states that facilitate $*OH$ adsorption and promote dynamic surface reconstruction under anodic polarization. Cobalt vacancies, predominantly formed during post-deposition annealing, alter the oxidation landscape by stabilizing $Co^{3+} \rightarrow Co^{4+}$ transitions, as supported by our experimental observation that the 30GC- Co_3O_4 sample—richest in cobalt vacancies—exhibited the lowest overpotential (343 mV at 10 mA cm^{-2}).

To further elucidate the role of these defects, Bader charge analysis was performed. The calculated charges for Co^{2+} (+1.40 q) and Co^{3+} (+1.47 q) indicate partial charge delocalization, consistent with a mixed-valence system. These findings are experimentally relevant, as the Co^{3+} sites in octahedral coordination serve as redox-active centers during the OER, with their availability and oxidation state being strongly modulated by the local vacancy environment [5,84]. Oxygen atoms, with a Bader charge of -1.08 q, exhibit deviation from the ideal -2 oxidation state due to covalent character and hybridization—an effect enhanced in defective regions and contributing to increased electronic conductivity. In summary, the computational results directly complement our experimental findings, offering a microscopic picture of how vacancy engineering—achieved via PECVD and thermal treatment—modulates the electronic structure and enhances the catalytic performance of Co_3O_4 thin films. The synergy between oxygen and cobalt vacancies plays a pivotal role in facilitating charge transport, lowering kinetic barriers, and stabilizing reactive intermediates, thereby providing a rational design framework for next-generation electrocatalysts.

4. Conclusions

This study highlights the essential roles of oxygen and cobalt vacancies in boosting the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) activity of cobalt oxide thin films. We deposited cobalt oxide films onto glassy carbon substrates using plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition (PECVD), followed by annealing at 400 °C. The PECVD process introduced oxygen vacancies in the as-deposited films, while the thermal annealing likely created cobalt vacancies. These dual vacancies, oxygen and cobalt, coexist in the films and are crucial to optimizing their OER performance.

The thin films transformed into a spinel Co_3O_4 structure, which plays a significant role in their catalytic behavior. Notably, the presence of both oxygen and cobalt vacancies led to the highest OER performance in the 30GC- Co_3O_4 sample, which displayed the highest concentration of cobalt vacancies. This sample achieved the lowest overpotential (343 mV at 10 mA cm^{-2}), showing a remarkable improvement in catalytic efficiency. This enhancement can be attributed to the synergistic effects of the vacancies: oxygen vacancies aid in structural reconstruction and promote stronger $*OH$ adsorption, while cobalt vacancies reduce the energy barrier for deprotonation and facilitate efficient Co^{3+}

→ Co⁴⁺ oxidation.

Moreover, it was also demonstrated that the thin films exhibited catalytic activity not only at the surface but also throughout their entire bulk and porosity of the film. This finding highlights the significance of deposition time and the resulting film thickness in determining OER performance. The increased active surface within the bulk of the film contributes to more efficient charge transfer and improved electrochemical behavior, thereby boosting the overall OER activity.

The study also integrates experimental data with DFT calculations, confirming the critical role of vacancies in optimizing electron transfer and enabling the generation of active oxyhydroxide species. Our findings suggest that PECVD, combined with controlled thermal treatment, is a promising technique for engineering cobalt-based electrocatalysts with tailored vacancy concentrations, offering a valuable path for designing high-performance OER catalysts. This research opens up new possibilities for further developments in the field, particularly in the precise control of vacancy engineering to optimize catalytic properties for a wide range of electrochemical applications.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Piotr Kuświk: Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Maciej Fronczak:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Stanisław Gierlotka:** Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Amil Aligayev:** Writing – original draft, Software, Investigation. **Ulkar Jabbarli:** Writing – original draft, Software, Investigation. **Francisco Javier Dominguez-Gutierrez:** Writing – original draft, Software, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Marta Gmurek:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Sebastian Arabasz:** Investigation, Visualization, Writing – review & editing. **Dominik Knozowski:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Aleksandra Kędzierska-Sar:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Robert Ranecki:** Writing – original draft, Investigation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Gmurek Marta reports financial support was provided by National Science Centre Poland. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.cattod.2025.115374](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cattod.2025.115374).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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